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IMPACT OF CRUDE OIL SPILLAGE ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY OF RURAL FARMERS IN DELTA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Many parts of Nigeria are experiencing occurrences of various natural and human induced environmental disasters. Crude oil is the main stay of the Nigeria economy, and its exploration and exploitation has brought with it several cases of oil spillage, leading to depletion of agricultural productivity. The study examined the impact of crude oil spillage on the agricultural productivity of rural farmers in Delta State. Specifically, the study examined the causes of oil spillage, effect and extent of oil spillage on agricultural land, effect of oil spillage on agricultural production and causes of agitation between the villagers and oil companies towards crude oil exploitation. Multistage sampling technique was employed in the selection of sample of 120 individuals. Data obtained for this study were analyzed using descriptive statistics and mean score. The result revealed that Pipeline vandalization by criminals (34%) and Negligence of oil companies (29%) were the major causes of oil spill in Aniocha South, Patani and Warri in Delta State. The result on effect of oil spillage on agricultural land and productivity showed that there is a negative effect because all the variables like: any oil producing plant in your area, turned hitherto productive areas into wastelands, cultivable plots are greatly reduced and infertile land for crop production respectively, were rated high and had an acceptable overall discrimination score ($x = \geq 2.50$). The result also revealed that majority of the farmers (67%) reported that about 30 – 40ha of agricultural land in the study area was affected by oil spill. The results further revealed that the major cause of agitation against oil companies and crude oil exploitation was lack of job opportunity to members of host communities (38%). Therefore, this study concludes that crude oil spillage had detrimental and negative effects on agricultural land and production. It is recommended that government should formulate policies that will help to control oil spillage on farmland.*

Keywords: Agricultural Productivity, Crude Oil, Oil Spillage, Rural Farmers

INTRODUCTION

Petroleum production and export plays a major role in Nigeria's economy and accounts for

about 90% of her gross earnings. The dominant role of oil in Nigeria has pushed agriculture from its prominent position in the early fifties

and sixties to the background. In addition, the country's over dependence on the oil sector, has led to a drop in other sectors like tourism, transportation, manufacturing and so on (Egubbe and Urhobotha, 2022). Agriculture is crucial to economic development of most developing nations as about 80% of the poor in Africa, Nigerian inclusive resides in rural areas and depends largely on subsistence farming for food and means of livelihood (Amusa *et al*, 2021). About 50 percent of the active labour force is engaged in one form of agricultural activity or another, with yam, cassava, plantain, maize, cocoyam and vegetables as the predominant food crops in the area. However, owing to the hydrographic conditions of the State only a fraction of the land size is cultivated with crops (Echetama *et al*, 2020). The hydrocarbons found in crude-oil spillage are large and complex molecules, and persistent in nature and may require a strong reagent to counteract their effects on agricultural soil (Essien and John, 2010).

Eze (2018) noted that environmental conditions, to a very large extent determine the yield and productivity of agriculture because the environment provides farmers with the resources such as water bodies, land, forest, vegetation and biodiversity for agricultural production. The increasing trend of pollution and oil spillage which have destroyed arable lands is not unconnected with poverty increase in the Niger Delta.

Oil spoilage, according to Echetama, *et al* (2020) is the presence of crude or refined oil on soil or sea water mostly due to human activities. Oil spillage cause significant damage to water and soil and also degrade most agricultural lands thus rendering them unproductive. In 2013 alone, the volume of oil spills in Niger Delta was about 20,000 barrels which negatively affected crops growth and yields in the region (Shell Petroleum Development Company [SPDC], 2015). Oil

spill is an unwitting release of liquid petroleum hydrocarbon into the environment as a result of human activities. They are usually mostly caused by accidents involving oil tankers, barges, refineries, pipelines and oil storage facilities. These unpleasant events are as a result of human errors and by natural disaster such as; earthquakes, deliberate acts by vandals, terrorists or militants (Egubbe and Urhobotha, 2022).

The rising cases of oil spillage in Niger Delta, Nigeria has further worsened soil infertility in the area resulting in destruction of soil micro-organisms and decreasing agricultural productivity of farmers in oil producing communities. In affirmation, Echetama, *et al* (2020) stated that the effect of oil spillage on farmlands has greatly hampered agricultural activities in Niger Delta including oil producing areas of Delta State as there have been records of oil spillage covering farming areas and water bodies resulting in loss of soil fertility, decrease in farm productivity and deterioration of farm produce.

Although the level of agricultural production in the State is somewhat low given the abundant resource endowment, Delta State is the largest crude oil producing State in Nigeria located in the Niger delta region, the base of the Nigerian oil and gas industry which generates over 90 percent of the nation's foreign exchange earnings. Paradoxically, in spite of the increasing revenue from crude oil exploitation, the communities from which this resource flows in the Niger Delta continue to live in conditions of social deprivation and abject poverty. All stages of oil exploitation impact negatively on the environment, and the greatest single intractable environmental problem caused by crude oil exploration in the Delta region is oil spillage (Anumet *et al*, 2020).

The environmental consequences of crude oil spillage on the inhabitants of Delta State are enormous. Oil spills have degraded most agricultural lands in the State and have turned hitherto productive areas into wastelands. With increasing soil infertility due to the destruction of soil micro-organisms, and dwindling agricultural productivity, farmers have been forced to abandon their land, to seek non-existent alternative means of livelihood. Aquatic life has also been destroyed with the pollution of traditional fishing grounds, exacerbating hunger and poverty in fishing communities (Anumetal, 2020).

In the Niger Delta, oil spill is perceived to be a major consequence of an inordinate exploitation of petroleum resources in the region Eze (2018). Oil exploration has over the years impacted negatively on the physical environment of the oil-bearing communities. Elum, *et al.*, (2016), observes that oil exploitation has increased the rate of environmental degradation and has perpetuated food insecurity as a result of death of fish and crops as well as loss of farm lands and viable rivers for fishing activities leading to loss of livelihood. There is no doubt that the disastrous effect of oil spill impedes agricultural productivity and fishing to be specific, which in the long-run has an adverse consequence on the economic life of the inhabitants of this region (Paul, 2015).

The effects of crude oil spills includes reduction of soil fertility, poor soil creation of farm land, degradation of farm land, increased soil temperature/toxicity, destruction of soil micro-organisms, destruction of soil structure,

low land productivity, yellowing of crop leaves, stunted growth of crop and so on. It is certain that most of the oil producing areas are heading for crises if all develop a lukewarm and nonchalant attitude towards oil exploration problems. This constant threat to life and property and continuous loss of land and water quality in the affected areas, including the study areas call for urgent attention. Therefore, it is against this background that this study was carried out to examine the impact of oil spillage on the agricultural land and production in oil producing communities of Delta State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined (1) the causes of oil spillage (2) effects of oil spillage on agricultural land (3) the extent of land affected (4) effects of oil spillage on agricultural production, and (5) causes of agitation against oil companies in the area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

THE STUDY AREA

This study was conducted in Delta, State, southern Nigeria. Delta State, which is one of the nine (9) States in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, lies roughly between longitudes 5°00 and 6°45'E and latitudes 5°00 and 6°30'N. The states bordering Delta State are Edo to the North, Ondo to the Northwest, Anambra to the East and Bayelsa and Rivers to the Southeast. On its Southern flank is 160 km of the coastline of the Bight of Benin. On the East and South the State is bounded by the lower course and Delta of the Niger River. The State covers about 6833 km² with a population of 4098391 people (NPC, 2006). The State comprises of 25 Local Government Areas (LGAs) and is greatly endowed with abundant natural resources and a weather which supports all year round agricultural production.

Figure 1: Delta State Showing the Sampled LGAs.

Source: Adapted from Delta State Map Jigsaw Puzzle.

INSTRUMENT OF DATA COLLECTION

The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed by the researcher to gather information from the respondents. The primary data collected for the study included the causes of oil spillage, effect of oil spillage on agricultural land, effect and extent of oil spillage on agricultural production and causes of agitation between the villagers and oil companies towards crude oil exploitation in the study areas.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Multistage sampling procedure was employed in the selection of sample. Delta State was purposively selected because of the predominance of oil production and spillage in the area, and the fact that agricultural production is the major occupation of the people. In the second stage, simple random

sampling was employed to select three LGAs from Delta State (Aniocha South, Patani and Warri North). Third stage involved the use of simple random sampling to select two (2) communities from each LGA making it six Communities. In the fourth stage, two villages were selected from each of the selected communities making twelve (12) Villages. Then, ten (10) respondents were randomly selected from each of the villages, making a total of one hundred and twenty (120) respondents for the study as sample size. The purpose of choosing simple random sampling is to eliminate bias and make sure the sample is representative of the entire population. Under this sampling design, every item of the universe has an equal chance of inclusion in the sample.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data obtained for this study were analyzed using descriptive statistics including frequency

count, percentages, chart and mean scores. The various attributes for the Likert scale were strongly agree (4); Agree (3); Disagree (2); Strongly disagree (1). Using the method of mean score analysis, a discriminating mean of 2.50 was produced. The mean value of each attribute equal to or above 2.50 ($x \geq 2.50$) was regarded as an accepted decision while attribute with mean value less than 2.50 ($x < 2.50$) was regarded as rejected decision.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CAUSES OF OIL SPILLAGE IN THE STUDY AREAS

The result on causes of oil spillage is presented in Figure 2. The result revealed that Pipeline vandalization (34%) and Negligence by oil

companies (29%) were the major cause of oil spill in Delta state. While the least causes was oil pilfering (4%). This implies that the management of oil companies in the study area exhibit nonchalant attitude on the implication of the effect of the occurrence of oil spillage on the host communities. The communities on their own part engage in illegal bunkering of oil which they believe they are justified to engage in without considering the negative effects. This was in line with the finding of Mba, *et al.*, (2019) that oil spillage in Nigeria has created and caused a lot of environmental and health problems. It means that crude oil can occur in form of spillages due to oil well blowout, corrosion of pipelines, accidental discharges and vandalisation. These oil spills can also be due to underground leakages which have impacts on the farm land.

Figure 2: Causes of oil spillage in the study area.
Source: Field survey, 2023

EFFECTS OF OIL SPILLAGE ON AGRICULTURAL LAND

The results of the analysis on effect of oil spillage on agricultural land is presented in Table 1, It was found that all the items listed on

effect of oil spillage on agricultural land were accepted because all the items like: any oil producing plant in your area, turned hitherto productive areas into wastelands, cultivable plots are greatly reduced and infertile land for crop production respectively, were rated high

and had an acceptable overall discrimination score ($x = \geq 2.50$). This implies that oil spillage has negative effect on agricultural land of Delta state. This is in agreement with the findings of Odjuvwuederhie (2006) that the environmental consequences of oil pollution on the inhabitants of Delta State are enormous. Oil spills have degraded most agricultural lands in the State and have turned hitherto productive areas into wastelands. With increasing soil infertility due

to the destruction of soil micro-organisms, and dwindling agricultural productivity, farmers have been forced to abandon their land, to seek non-existent alternative means of livelihood. Aquatic life have also been destroyed with the pollution of traditional fishing grounds, exacerbating hunger and poverty in fishing communities. The study generally showed that there is a great negative effect of oil spillage on agricultural land in Delta State.

Table 1: Effects of oil spillage on agricultural land
Multiple responses recorded

S/N	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total Score	Mean Score	Remark
		4	3	2	1			
		F Score	F Score	F Score	F Score			
1	Is there any oil producing plant in your area	100 400	10 30	4 8	6 6	444	3.7	Acceptance
2	turned hitherto productive areas into wastelands	95 380	20 60	3 6	2 2	448	3.733	Acceptance
3	Cultivable plots are greatly reduced	106 424	10 30	2 4	2 2	460	3.833	Acceptance
4	Infertile land for crop production	105 420	9 27	2 4	4 4	455	3.792	Acceptance

Source: Field survey, 2023

EXTENT OF AGRICULTURAL LAND AFFECTED BY OIL SPILLAGE IN THE STUDY AREA

As a matter of fact, agriculture remains the backbone of the economy of the oil producing area, but the land is always

subjected to crude oil spillage. Any damage done to the land always constitutes a threat to economic development of an area. As reported by majority (67%) of the farmers the agricultural land in the study area affected by oil spill was about 30 – 40ha, which means

large areas of farm land were abandoned because of oil spillage in the study area (Figure 3). Reason for abandoning the affected areas is likely due to declining

productivity. This is not surprising because the average output per farm cultivated in polluted farmland will not yield as high as in non-polluted farmland.

Figure 3: Extent oil spill affected agricultural land in the study area

Source: Field survey, 2023

EFFECT OF OIL SPILLAGE ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

The study revealed that oil spill has a negative effect on crop yield and germination, land productivity and farm income in a manner consistent with economic expectation. As seen in Table 2 the farmers accepted that fishing is no longer a lucrative business, oil spills are driving all seafood away, some plants crops had stunted growth, crops are prevented from germinating, there is scarcity of suitable vegetables and crop yield is very low. Which implies that crude oil spillage has effect on agricultural productivity in Delta of Nigeria because all variables under study were rated high and had an acceptable overall discrimination score ($x \geq 2.50$). This is in agreement with the work by Mba, *et al.*, (2019),

who opined that the negative impact of oil spill on crop production as farm income is depressed due to the twin effects of land degradation and poor plant growth. There is a very significant changes given the dearth of fertile arable land in the region; itself a consequence of land degradation. The oil spill dummy appeared to exert the greatest impact on farm income, as a 10 percent increase in spillage will decrease farm income by as much as 5 percent. This implies that there is a sharp decline in agricultural output due to oil spillage. This study of Odjuvwuederhie (2006) also shows that crop yield, land productivity and farm income before and after the incidence of spills indicate that oil spill has a significant effect on crop yield, land productivity as well as farm income

Table 2: Effects of oil spill on agricultural production

S / N	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total Score	Mean Score	Remarks
		4	3	2	1			
		F Score	F Score	F Score	F Score			
1	Fishing is no longer a lucrative business	88 352	12 36	14 28	6 6	422	3.51 7	Acceptance
2	Oil spills are driving all seafood away	84 336	6 18	17 34	13 13	401	3.34 2	Acceptance
3	Some plants crops had stunted growth	68 272	2 6	29 58	21 21	357	2.97 5	Acceptance
4	Crops are prevented from germinating	90 360	20 60	7 14	3 3	437	3.64 2	Acceptance
5	There is scarcity of suitable vegetables	20 80	60 180	15 30	25 25	315	2.62 5	Acceptance
6	Crop yield is very low	61 244	14 42	5 10	40 40	336	2.8	Acceptance

Source: Field survey, 2023

CAUSES OF AGITATION AGAINST OIL COMPANIES INVOLVED IN EXPLOITATION OF CRUDE OIL IN THE STUDY AREA

Figure 4 show the results of causes of agitation by villagers against oil companies involved in crude oil exploitation was due to no job opportunity given to the host community (38%), No adequate compensation (25%) while

the least was no room for negotiations between the host community and oil company management. Results from oral interview also supported the opinion that the people don't have access to clean water. Thus, they are forced to depend on polluted streams for water for drinking and other domestic uses. The chemicals released into the environments are slowly killing the occupants and indigenes of the Niger Delta.

Figure 4: Causes of agitation against oil companies in the study area

Source: Field survey, 2023

Although, multiple legal frameworks, like the Oil Pipelines Act, the National Oil Spill Contingency Plan and the Petroleum Act that provide for compensation exist, but they fail to explicitly state in financial terms what the affected communities should get. They leave room for negotiations between the affected communities and the polluter which, in some cases, have led to prolonged litigations. Also, the affected companies have the responsibility to clean up the polluted communities but, just as in compensation, they default. Poverty is rife in Niger Delta Communities (Nwafor, 2022).

CONCLUSION

Oil spillage has caused incalculable damages to the economy and social activities of the host communities. The disaster has destroyed the existing biodiversity of the delicate ecosystem and the resultant pollution also has detrimental and negative effects on agricultural land and production in the study area. To this effect the

oil companies have deprived the communities those previous endowment from nature and no adequate compensation was given to the affected people.

It was concluded that oil pollution on farm land and ecosystem is mostly disastrous to the entire economy of the state and is a major contributor to soil and land degradation, environmental pollution, ecological discontinuity, soil value loss, deforestation, low vegetation, depopulation of both domestic animals and wildlife and extinction of aquatic life. The study was carried out in order to review the negative implications of oil spillage on farmers' agricultural productivity and set back on the general economy. It is expected that the result of the study will form reference material for further academic research on the impact of oil spillage on agricultural land and production. In addition, the study will help the government to formulate sustainable policies that will help

to reduce oil spillage on farmlands, thereby, reducing the detrimental effects on local communities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to ameliorate the observed negative and detrimental effects of crude oil spill on agricultural land and production in Delta State, Nigeria, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Enforcement of environmental laws by government over oil spillage should be done to protect farm lands and the interest of farmers.
- ii. Government, oil companies and individuals should be actively involved in the war against crude oil spillage.
- iii. Commensurate amount of compensation should be paid to affected people in line with the economic trends in the country.

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